

Populations of parasitic nematodes of grain legumes in rice-based cropping patterns in four environments and flooding regimes in the Philippines

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Plant parasitic nematodes of the genera *Rotylenchulus* and *Meloidogyne* are important grain legume pests in the Philippines. Those genera do not attack graminaceous crops such as rice and corn in rice cropping patterns. A study was undertaken at the target area of the IRRI-Bureau of Plant Industry Cropping Systems Program in Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines, to determine the nematode incidence in four common rice-growing environments, each distinguished by duration of flooding:

1. well-drained, non-puddled fields planted to upland rice (non-flooded);
2. isolated rice paddies in drainageways among upland fields, where a crop of transplanted rice is flooded from 2 to 3 months during the rainy season;
3. paddies in lowland areas of alkaline soil that are flooded highly intermittently. Alternate flooding (no more than 1–2 weeks) and draining of such paddies alleviates iron and zinc deficiencies; and
4. normal lowland rainfed paddies with good water retention during rice cultivation (flooded for 2-3 months).

Soil and root samples were taken from mungbeans or cowpeas planted after the single rice crop in four replicated fields for each environment. Soil samples from each field were pooled and nematodes were extracted by the Baermann funnel technique. Roots were stained with acid fuchsin-lactophenol and examined under a microscope.

The results indicated that flooding during rice culture, even intermittently, is an effective cultural method for controlling plant parasitic nematodes (see table). Only in the well-drained, non-flooded, upland environment did we find very high nematode populations capable of reducing yields of legumes planted after rice.

Plant parasitic nematode populations in mung beans and cowpeas following rice in four environments. ^{a/} Pangasinan, Philippines, 1976.			
Environment	Nematodes (no./250 cc soil and 1 g roots)		
	<i>Rotylenchulus</i>	<i>Meloidogyne</i>	Total of 7 genera ^{b/}
Upland fields	56	431	551
Isolated paddies in drainageways among upland fields	2	0	17
Highly intermittently flooded fields	2	5	35
Normal rainfed paddies	1	0	3

^{a/} Av. of 4 fields in each environmental condition having a similar cropping pattern during the previous 3 years.

^{b/} *Rotylenchulus*, *Meloidogyne*, *Criconemoides*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Hoplolaimus*, *Pratylenchus*, *Tylenchorhynchus*

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